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ABSTRACT

Induction motors have long been recognized for their simple rugged construction. To date, however, their application to variable speed or servo drives has been hampered by limitations on their control. Induction motor drives have tended to be complex and to display troublesome low speed characteristics due in part to nonsinusoidal driving voltages.

A new technique has been developed which involves direct synthesis of sinusoidal driving voltages from a high frequency power bus and independent control of frequency and voltages. Separation of frequency and voltage allows independent control of rotor and stator flux, full four quadrant operation, and instantaneous torque control.

Recent test results, current status of the technology, and proposed aerospace applications will be discussed.

INTRODUCTION

This paper will discuss previous and ongoing work at NASA Lewis Research Center in the general area of aerospace electromechanical actuators (EMA's).

It has been recognized for some time that electromechanical actuators have many potential advantages over hydraulic actuators. Certain technical limitations, however, have prevented their adaptation in large (multihorsepower) applications.

Among the generally accepted advantages of EMA's are reduced maintenance, adaptability to built-in-testing (BITE), improved reliability, and greatly improved efficiency (typically 10:1 or more) (Fig. 1)[1]. The time is ripe for application of EMA's, as customers are recognizing their great advantage in reducing the life cycle cost of ownership.

PRESENT APPROACH TO EMA'S

Brushless dc motors

Historically, aerospace EMA's have used "brushless dc" motors. These are in reality permanent magnet synchronous ac motors requiring electronic inversion and control circuitry. There have been several technical limitations to the general application of brushless dc motors, which become overwhelming in large aerospace actuators.

One problem inherent in permanent field excitation concerns failure modes and their accommodation. In the case of a shorted stator winding or its associated drive circuitry, the motor becomes an uncontrollable load upon the rest of the system. While it has been proposed to accommodate single event failures with mechanical differentials, explosive clutches, etc., failure accommodation for multiple failures has become very difficult [2]. The permanent magnets are generally located in the rotor to minimize rotor loss. They are inherently fragile, however, and have a definite temperature limitation due to the Curie point transition of the permanent magnets.

While these first two limitations concern brushless dc motors in general, another problem has limited their application in large, multiple-horsepower, aerospace actuators. Typically, these motors have been driven from hard switched sources having turn off losses which are proportional to frequency. Additionally, voltage regulation is generally accomplished by pulse width (squarewave) modulation. Such waveforms cause increased motor losses due to their rich harmonic content (Fig. 2). In addition, the filtering required will be physically large due to the low machine frequency involved. When harmonic content and filter requirements are reduced by increasing switching rates, circuit complexities and losses rapidly increase. The effect of these limitations is such that the drive circuitry for large brushless dc motors is typically many times the size of the motor itself.

Switched Reluctance Motors

More recently high saliency, switched reluctance motors have been advocated for actuators (Fig. 3). One advantage realized is the avoidance of mechanical lock up under stator fault conditions. Another often cited advantage is that only half as many electronic switches are required. Since these switches, however, must carry twice the current as the motor power increases, doubling switch current becomes a devil's bargain when dealing with I^2 phenomena, such as leakage reactance energy. Low speed operation of switched reluctance machines becomes increasingly rough as the operating speed reduces toward that of a stepper motor. In spite of these limitations, switched reluctance machines are becoming popular in lower power applications, particularly in the United Kingdom [3]. However, their suitability for high power servo applications remains to be demonstrated.

Induction Motors

Induction motors have, in general, been acknowledged to be not only rugged and relatively inexpensive, but are also considered to be relatively inefficient and difficult to control speed. Several recent technical developments have overcome these limitations and allow use of the induction motor in a wide range of applications, which exploit its robustness, its high temperature capabilities, and its immunity to stator shorts.

PULSE POPULATION MODULATION

The key to these developments centers upon the use of a high frequency, sinusoidal voltage source. All switching is accomplished using integral half cycles of energy. In the typical case of a 20-kHz power link waveform, zero crossings occur every 25 μ s [4].

By utilizing the self commutating characteristic of the ac carrier, the frequency proportional turn-off loss is avoided. Also, the reduced stress in the semiconductor switch allows control of higher power for a given switching device.

In general, line frequencies much less than 20 kHz are required to operate a motor. Such lower frequencies are synthesized from the 20 kHz half-sinusoids, using pulse population modulation (PPM) (Fig. 4). Using a pulse population modulated waveform, the line frequency is controlled by the waveform pattern, while the effecting voltage is controlled by the population density of the pulses. As a result, the frequency and voltage of the synthesized waveform may be independently varied and controlled.

V/f RATIO CONTROL

In its simplest electrical sense, an induction motor is a transformer with a primary (stator) and a short circuited secondary (rotor) (Fig. 5). Again, on a first order basis, the rotating (stator) magnetic flux is proportional to the voltage to frequency ratio (V/f). The short circuit (secondary) current is proportional to the voltage induced by the difference in speed (slip) between the stator field and the rotor. By monitoring the rotor speed and controlling the synthesized (stator) frequency the induced frequency in the rotor (slip), and consequently the rotor current itself is controlled.

In this manner, waveforms synthesized by pulse population modulation allow the stator and rotor currents to be independently controlled [5]. Also, since the stator voltage is synthesized from a high frequency (e.g., 20 kHz) carrier, the rotor current and torque are variable at a nearly instantaneous rate. Additionally, the phase of the rotor current may be controlled to allow both positive and negative torques to be produced. This allows full four quadrant energy control (Fig. 6)[6]. Three important phenomena are illustrated by (Fig. 6(a)); (1) starting with an induction machine motoring at constant speed, the torque is instantly reversed causing a reverse of energy flow (generation); (2)

the torque is held constant through zero speed, at which point the rotation reverses (motoring); (3) once the desired reverse speed is reached, the torque again changes instantly to allow constant speed operation.

While the discussion so far applies to induction machines in general, two related characteristics make high frequency population density synthesis very attractive for high power applications. Most importantly, all switching is accomplished at zero current. This soft switching avoids the frequency proportional switching loss, thus allowing high frequency, low distortion, current synthesis. The low distortion synthesized current in turn reduces motor loss. Another advantage of high frequency synthesis is the greatly reduced size of the energy storage elements (capacitors and inductors) required for isolation, energy storage, and interference control. Since these elements are operated at the carrier frequency, rather than at the synthesized frequency as in other systems, their physical size is greatly reduced. It is, therefore, the increased efficiency and reduced driver component size that will allow packaging motor controllers in much smaller, more rugged configurations and thereby make high power electromechanical actuators practical.

CURRENT STATUS

High frequency power distribution systems have been brought to a high level of maturity through work performed for the NASA Space Station Freedom [7]. The joint Air Force/NASA Advanced Launch System (ALS) program has identified electromechanical actuators as a key element in their Advanced Development Program. Several contracts have been let with major contractors to develop EMA's for both engine control and thrust vector control. Breadboard demonstrations will begin in 1989, with full power (25 hp) demonstrations scheduled in early 1990. Other applications of high frequency power under consideration involve both civilian transport and military aircraft.

CONCLUSIONS

Electromechanical actuators have clearly come of age. Technical advances involving high frequency power management will allow the use of induction motors in a wide range of applications that have not been previously considered appropriate.

REFERENCES

1. Hoffman, A.C., et al.: Advanced Secondary Power System for Transport Aircraft. NASA TM-2463, 1985.
2. Edge, J.T.: An Electromechanical Actuator Technology Development Program. SAE Paper 780581, Apr. 1978.
3. Lawrenson, P.J., et al.: Variable Speed Switched Reluctance Motors. IEE Proc. Electric Power Appl., Vol. 127, Pt. B, no. 4, pp. 253-265.

4. Mildice, J.: In Space It's 20 kHz AC Power. Power Technics Magazine, vol. 5, no. 2, Feb. 1989, pp. 29-32.
5. Sood, P.K.; Lipo, T.A.; and Hansen, I.G.: A Versatile Power Converter for High Frequency Link Systems. IEEE Trans. Power Electron., vol. 3, no. 4, Oct. 1988, pp. 383-390.

6. Lipo, T.A.; and Sood, P.K.: Study of the Generator/Motor Operation of Induction Machines in a High Frequency Link Space Power System. NASA CR-179600, 1986.
7. Hansen, I.G.: Status of 20 kHz Space Station Power Distribution Technology. NASA TM-100781, 1988.

FIGURE 1. - CHART SHOWING ADVANTAGES OF ELECTROHYDROSTATIC ACTUATORS OVER CENTRAL HYDRAULICS (WPAEB STUDY).

FIGURE 2. - TYPICAL SIX STEP INVERTER WAVEFORMS AND RESULTING SINE WAVE PWM WAVEFORMS.

FIGURE 3. - GEOMETRY OF HIGH SALIENCY SWITCHED RELUCTANCE MOTOR.

FIGURE 4. - SYNTHESIS OF A BALANCED SET OF VOLTAGES HAVING SINUSOIDAL FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY IS 400 Hz WITH A MODULATION INDEX OF 0.9.

FIGURE 5. - EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT OF THE POLYPHASE MOTOR. IRON LOSSES DUE TO THE MAIN FLUX NEGLECTED.

(a) SPEED REVERSAL OF 2-hp MACHINE.

(b) PDM CONVERTER SYSTEM OPERATION.

FIGURE 6. - INDUCTION MACHINE UNDER BOTH MOTORING AND GENERATION.